

VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF TASKA SERVICES QUALITY INSTRUMENT

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ABSTRACT

Survey questionnaires are one of the most extensively used data-gathering approaches in social science research. In this research, the primary aim of a survey is to collect crucial data in the most precise and reliable method achievable. This study aims to determine the reliability and construct validity of the constructed instrument in determining the contributing components to TASKA service attribution. This article examines and covers the validity and reliability of a survey questionnaire and the many types of validity and reliability tests used in TASKA to measure service quality. 273 TASKAs were chosen using the proportionate stratified random selection approach from three states in Malaysia's Klang Valley. The measurement model's validity and reliability in the analysis utilizing the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method. The fit index (CMF)² = 3230.541, with degrees of freedom (df) = 902, CMIN / df = 3.582 (5.0), CFI & TLI (0.9), and RMSEA = 0.070 (0.1), was used to fit the measurement models. According to the findings, all indices fulfil the standardized measure, and the assessment tool has proven to be beneficial. According to the research, five factors influence caretakers' evaluations of TASKA's service quality. With demographic factors like highest education level, profession, locality, home-TASKA range, type of agency, TASKA status, and child age helping to strengthen the TASKA selection factor, the management, kid's growth, charges, routine activity, and managing cost creates a strong association that can be used to estimate a complete structured equation model. The TASKA service model, according to studies, can be used to enhance present quality and predict future developments. It can also be used as a module for providing the maximum degree of service to the attribution of the caretakers.

Keywords – Validity, Reliability, Measurement Model, Structural Model, Goodness-of-fit index

INTRODUCTION

In Education, Human Resource Management is a set of strategies and procedures for incorporating and retaining teachers in schools to fulfil their mission and satisfy the goals for which they were founded (Silver et al., 2017). Even the most casual viewers will conclude that high-performing schools will be prioritized, and low-performing schools will be the last resort (Y. Tadik, G. L. Brown, & S. C. Mangelsdorf, 2020). Human resource management in education is concerned

mainly with a few primary issues; assessing, satisfying, maintaining, and improving the staff needs and services.

The empirical evidence regarding service quality satisfaction is examined in this study. The study focuses on the aspects that determine customer satisfaction with service quality, such as management system, fees, cost allocation, children's growth, and activities. Outcome determinants are also investigated at the organizational and individual levels (Scheiner et al., 2016). Academics, literature, and success management receive special attention on the educational path (Papadaki et al., 2019).

The role of the caregiver or child care worker is very important in providing high-quality child care in the development of future leaders. For the next generation to grow, child care centers need to enhance and stimulate quality assurance practices among staff. The study goal was to validate the aspects that have an effect on caretakers' perceptions of TASKA's quality services (management system, fees, cost allocation, kids' growth, and activities) in three Malaysian regions. The study's specific objectives are to evaluate the created survey instrument's reliability and assess the research instrument design's validity. Stratified random sampling techniques were used to select respondents from registered childcare centers in Selangor, Wilayah Persekutuan, and Putrajaya.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

As a multivariate technique, Structural equation modelling (SEM) is employed to test and analyze multivariate causal links that are increasingly being employed in scientific studies (Briere et al., 2017). Researchers, instructors, and students are increasingly turning to this strategy. This is due to the ability to deliver precise and timely estimates due to the flexibility and depth of coverage (Jacobucci et al., 2017). The SEM analysis includes procedures such as model requirements, data collecting, planning, understanding, and model modification (Godbout et al., 2019). To assure the model's acceptance and rejection, the validity of this index value must be recognized (Garn & Webster, 2018). This data is being used in an assessment to help TASKA, a Malaysian early childcare centre with locations throughout the Klang Valley, improve its services. The results of this survey were used to calculate the key contributing element to teachers' attribution of caretakers' eyesight.

Subjects

To fit the model in this study, 273 TASKA from Malaysia's Klang Valley (Selangor, Wilayah Persekutuan, and Putrajaya) were sampled. Individuals who worked at the TASKA service directly with the various facilities supplied were the survey's respondents. The services are given, characteristics of caretaking, management structure, fees, activities, children's growth, and cost have all been identified as mediating variables. All these characteristics are judged as the level of caregivers' attribution through employee views. These many viewpoints serve as intermediary variables, which are critical to the study's effectiveness. The information came from a survey performed using a questionnaire that had been thoroughly tested for accuracy. To proportional population values, the stratified random sample method is utilized. The best model of fit and structural analysis was performed using statistical software. SEM consists of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), Discriminant Validity (DV) and Path Analysis (PA). The SEM can dissect and decide the contributing elements of service quality to the type of facilities supplied and gauge the level of caregiver attribution made by TASKA caretakers.

To approximate the population value from which the sample was accumulated, sampling is necessary to acquire the sample value or size. Because the samples have a lower degree of variability than the population, this saves time, energy, and money. The population's variability is often dispersed, resulting in a normal distribution graph. As a result, the sample size should be calculated so that inferential statistics can be performed. N is 273 TASKAs for the computation of the minimal sample size using the limited population approach, stratified sampling.

In Social science investigation, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is often employed as the initial step. A more advanced version of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is used to see if the actions are consistent with the researchers' goals. As a result, the CFA's goal is to correct the data to match the predicted measurement model. The range to which the projected model has a covariance that connects all elements in the simulation is then assessed using model fit measures.

Data Analysis

SPSS and AMOS software Version 23.0 were used to collect, encode, and analyze all study data. The data were first filtered prior to analysis to perceive the true elements. Data filtering has proven critical to providing precise data evaluation and acceptable normalcy distribution (Coakes & Steed, 1999). In addition, screening was done to see if there were any missing values resulting from respondents' inability to complete the questionnaires, which could affect data analysis. The following criteria were used to determine the component concept's convergent validity: standardized regression coefficients of observed variables less than 0.50, construct reliability (CR) less than 0.7, and average variance extracted (AVE) less than 0.5, as shown in Table 1 below. Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) were used in the data analysis procedure. The goodness-of-fit index was additionally verified using the Chi-square test, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), Discriminant Validity (DCV), Path Analysis (PA), and SEM test.

Table 1: Acceptance level of indices

Name of Category	Level of Acceptance
Factor Loading	Weight > 0.8 (Kharuddin et al., 2020)
Absolute Fit	P value < 0.05, Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation < 0.10, Goodness-of-Fit Indices > 0.9, (Shipley, 2016)
Incremental Fit	Comparative Fit Index > 0.9, Tucker Lewis Index > 0.9, (Silver, 2017)
Parsimonious Fit	Chi-square/df < 5.0, (Kharuddin et al., 2020)

Models can be evaluated using structured equation modelling (SEM) depending on the benefits of variable adaption (Anderson et al., 1982). This strategy is becoming increasingly popular among researchers, professors, and students. This is due to the flexibility and depth of options to provide accurate and timely predictions (Anderson et al., 1988). Model specification, data collection, budgeting, interpretation, and model update are the steps in SEM analysis (Anderson et al., 1988). The Structured Equation Modeling method is utilized to assess the benefits of model fit using Linear Multiple Regression (MLR) data. Pearson's correlation coefficient revealed the association between TASKA service quality and the mediating variable for criteria validity. Cronbach's alpha correlation coefficient was used to ensure internal consistency.

Convergence validity

Several approaches were used to determine face validity; an original questionnaire was subjected to regular editing before being given to a panel of experts comprised of six early childhood education professionals. They were requested to complete the survey questionnaire, and only a few remarks were received, triggering some reasonable revisions to improve precision. It recompenses the greatest variance with related factors by extracting the latent construct from other variables. For example, the cleaning activity (i.e., physical environment, children's sensitivity to TASKA, and physical hygiene, Berti et al., 2019) is used to quantify the management component as a latent variable. All of the research constructs had a Chi-square value of less than 5.0 over degrees of freedom (Chi Sq/df), indicating a parsimonious fit. Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) and Comparative-Fit Index (CFI) values beyond 0.5 were also found in the service quality constructs. Only in TASKA's children's service quality did the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) rating fall below 0.10. As a result, when hypothesizing a latent variable, one should be concerned about the reason for doing so. Physical environment and kids' compassion are latent variables that account for the link in the dataset in the management factor example described above. Shao et al. (2015) used CFA to condense the cleanliness activity features into a single variable that considered the physical surroundings, the children's sensitivity to TASKA, and physical hygiene. In addition, Capmouteres and Anand (2016) introduced Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to accept or reject measurement theories. Another sort of factor analysis, in addition to CFA, is exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Both use the same statistical estimating technique. Confirmatory factor analysis was used to assess the construct validity for each item related to TASKA service quality Instrument. This measurement model's convergent and discriminant validity must be determined first. The Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI) revealed that the cut-off values for five parameters, Chi-square/df, TLI, CFI, RMSEA, and p-value, are > 0.8, > 0.8, 0.10, and 0.05, respectively, with cut-off values of 5.0. (Kharuddin et al., 2020). Table 2 was used to evaluate all of the parameters. The remaining factors were computed with MLR to further formulate the variable weightage.

Table 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis result for the measurement model

Construct	Item	Factor Loading	Convergence validity	
			Composite reliability (>0.7)	Average variance extracted (>0.5)
Demographic	EducationF	0.852	0.881	0.772
	EducationM	0.896		
	EducationG	0.715		
	OccupationF	0.747		
	OccupationM	0.887		
	Distance	0.784		
	Location	0.821		
	Agency	0.808		
	Status	0.844		
	Kid_Age1	0.830		
Manage	Manage1	0.884	0.786	0.682
	Manage2	0.871		
	Manage3	0.793		
Fees	Fee1	0.889	0.893	0.705
	Fee2	0.883		
	Fee3	0.906		
	Fee4	0.934		

	Fee5	0.931		
Cost	Cost1	0.976		
	Cost2	0.974		
	Cost4	0.959	0.807	0.871
	Cost5	0.972		
	Activity	Activity1	0.897	
	Activity2	0.902		
	Activity3	0.909		
	Activity4	0.873	0.910	0.822
	Activity5	0.904		
	Activity6	0.889		
Grow	Grow1	0.816		
	Grow2	0.834	0.883	0.698
	Grow3	0.831		
Service Quality	SQ1	0.747		
	SQ2	0.831		
	SQ3	0.784		
	SQ4	0.854	0.777	0.702
	SQ5	0.844		
	SQ6	0.842		

Discriminant validity

Table 3 displays the dependability values for the numerous item constructs, with the average variance extracted (AVE) in a diagonal format bolded. The constructions' Cronbach alpha scores range from 0.78 to 0.89, indicating that they are all dependable and convergent. Particularly, the results in Table 3 show that both validities are met.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity Using Pearson Correlations and the AVE Score

	No of the original items	of the scale	Alpha	1	2	3	4	5
Manage (1)	4		0.87	0.88				
Fees (2)	2		0.80	0.76	0.78			
Cost (3)	2		0.78	0.65	0.65	0.85		
Activity (4)	2		0.77	0.68	0.73	0.77	0.83	
Grow (5)	2		0.83	0.76	0.69	0.69	0.74	0.89

To test the reliability coefficient, Cronbach (1951), face, construct, and convergent validity, several methodologies were applied. To determine face validity, a panel of experts consisting of two academics from the Department of Early Childhood Education, one HR practitioner, and a few senior lecturers whom all worked near the author's workplace were given an initial survey questionnaire. They were requested to complete the survey questionnaire, and only a few comments were received, prompting some modest revisions to improve clarity.

Measurement model

Statistical analysis has been employed in social science research for over a century. With the use of computer skills, statistical decision-making has increased considerably. Researchers must use univariate and bivariate analysis and complex multivariate research data analysis approaches like Structural Equation Modeling to comprehend data linkages. Create regression equalities to show how endogenous designs (predicted endogenous) are linked to exogenous constructions (predictive exogenous) in such circumstances (Yilmaz et al., 2016). Moreover, to benefit from a multivariate statistical investigation method that has a large application area in combining estimation standards such as structural equation modelling (SEM) (Hair et al., 1998).

SEM is a reliable examination method that combines multivariate statistical strategies. It is a useful testing model for furthering the development of techniques for empowering hypothetical models. In blended speculations, SEM can clarify the conditions and logical results relationship of the elements. SEM would not have any issues observing data with a tiny sample size (Gignac, G. E. 2006). To generate a complete structure, this technique relies on various measuring models. Quantitative combinations and correlation or causal assumptions are used in SEM procedures (Zainudin, 2012; Shipley, 2016; Lachowicz et al., 2018; Ning et al., 2019). SEM can also evaluate items under the latent construction in an indirect manner. Because it is only a hypothesized study topic, the latent construct is a variable that cannot be directly measured. SEM can be used to test conventional models since it is a continuation of general relapse research, which makes more than each regression examination in turn. In any event, the SEM is an unexpectedly useful tool in situations with more complicated relationships (corroborative component research, time series, and so on). It checks the adequacy of the assessed covariance network when it is created, as per hypothetical construction, of the covariance lattice of observed information (Hox and Bechger, 1995).

RESULTS

The model utilized in this study contained a sample of 273 mothers, dads, and guardians from various types of TASKA on Malaysia's east coast. Individuals who used TASKA services directly using the various facilities available were the survey's respondents. SEM is an extraordinary statistical method for illustrating interactions after regression analysis. It can deal with nonlinear circumstances and allow independent variables to be correlated. This covers the model's measurement errors and exposes and tests the link between numerous independent and latent dependent variables. Each of them is assessed using many observed variables. SEM is a corroborative construction, whereas the other multivariate statistical procedures are explanatory and highlight illustratively.

Furthermore, a speculation test reveals the dominating sides of SEM and corrects its measurement inaccuracies (Anderson, 2004). As a result, because correlation, regression, and component analysis are limited, SEM can be used to clarify schoolchildren's art activities. With a mean age of 35.91 16.60 years, the research population included 88 males (32.23%) and 185 females (67.76%). There were 202 married people (66.0%), 92 single people (30.1%), and 12 widowed or divorced people (3.9%) among them. Furthermore, 260 (84.9%) were employed, while 46 (15.1%) were unemployed.

Facilities supplied, features of care, policies, nourishment and safety were all found as mediating variables. These determinants are evaluated in terms of consumer satisfaction from three parent/guardian viewpoints. These various points of view serve as mediating variables in this research. The information came from a survey done using a questionnaire that had been proven to be reliable. Because there are different population values depending on the state and kind of

TASKA, the strata random sampling approach is utilized. Almost all items (25/27) had a content validity index of 0.80 to 1.00 at the item level and a scale-level content validity index/AVE of 0.90, indicating adequate content validity.

Two numerical form metrics – skewness and excess kurtosis – can be employed to assess normality statistically. If the skewness is not near to zero, the data gathering is not evenly dispersed. To determine the normality of the data utilized in this study, we looked at the skewness and kurtosis. The skewness of all measured variables was between 0.01 and 1.15 (absolute value) and less than 3; the kurtosis was between 0.04 and 1.41 (absolute value). The data followed a normal distribution. According to the multivariate normality test, the critical ratio was 14.2, and the multivariate kurtosis was 43.5. The collective frequency distributions for all variables are unclear, and few data support the multivariate normality assumption. As a result, if a univariate normality test yields no significant results, multivariate normality is believed to be satisfied (Collier, 2020). In conclusion, the study's assessed variables supported univariate normality, and thus, the validity of the TASKA service quality was acceptable.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

According to Maydeu-Olivares et al. (2019), the load factor for the newly designed scale must be more than 0.5. All components with lower factor loading values of 0.5 are excluded from the 'construction' in this study to assure unidimensionality, parsimonious, incremental, and absolute fit. According to the analysis, 43 items were deleted since their factor loading was less than 0.5. According to the researcher, the item is not excessively weak, but it does have a small factor loading of between 0.3 and 0.49.

Table 4: Summary of Latent Constructs Fitness

Construct				Incremental		Parsimonious	Absolute
	Chi-square	Df	P-value	TLI	CFI	Chi-square/Df	RMSEA
Activity	14.816	4	0.000	0.780	0.868	3.704	0.084
Cost	22.986	5	0.000	0.766	0.883	4.797	0.043
Fees	5.104	2	0.000	0.946	0.982	2,551	0.097
Manage	8.539	2	0.000	0.848	0.949	4.270	0.021

The suitability indicators of all unobserved constructs (latent) in the model are shown in Table 4. Constructive mediators, such as activity, cost, fees, and manage factors, have a Chi-Square/df value of less than 5.0, indicating that the mediators have reaped the benefits of the sparse fitness test. The TLI and CFI values in this construct model are greater than 0.7, while the RMSEA is less than 0.10. As a result, greater and complete fitness has been attained.

The correlations between all constructs are greater than 0.70. It can be determined that discriminant validity has been achieved, and no finalized constructs in the model need to be removed. It may be determined that all four fitness requirements for this model were met. The Chi-Square / Df and RMSEA values show that this model has a goodness-of-fit because the Chi-Square / Df value is 3.582, which is less than 5.0, and the RMSEA value is 0.070, which is less than 0.10. The detailed result can be seen in Table 5 and Figure 1.

Table 5: Goodness-of-fit Model

Figure 1: Measurement Model

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

More noteworthy consequences can be noticed from the goodness-of-fit model that meets the mediation provisions using the CFI and TLI indices and the significant values of the RMSEA precision level, based on the results attained through the path analysis tactic and structural model. Not all determinants in latent variables are taken into account when using the SEM method. Items numbered Fac1, Fac3, Fac6, Fac7, Fac8, and Fac9 with load values greater than 0.5 were extended in the construction of the best model for facility determinants. Parents/guardians discovered that their satisfaction with TASKA services in terms of facilities is influenced by their children's activity space (Fac1), dressing room (Fac3), playroom (Fac6), sleeping room (Fac7), lactation room (Fac8), and isolation chambers for infectious illness quarantine (Fac9). While their children are in TASKA, parents/guardians also highlight the need for safety. The preparedness of TASKA's first aid (Safety10), the presence of barrier doors that restrict children to the kitchen (Safety12), outside play equipment (Safety14), and an outdoor playground (Safety15) are all determining factors in their degree of happiness (Safety16). Apart from that, the TASKA staff's commitment to hygiene is the primary reason for parents'/guardians' decision to send their children to a TASKA. The cleanliness around the TASKA before the operation (Cleanliness1), the

physical environment (Cleanliness²), sensitivity to the current health of the TASKA youngsters (Cleanliness⁴), and the physical hygiene procedures used by the TASKA staff are just a few of the reasons (Cleanliness⁵). Parents and guardians have many motivations for selecting a TASKA. The primary elements that influence their decision are the distance of the TASKA from home, the medium's language, the fees charged, the curriculum supplied, and the age of their children. Where the best total effect for this method is 0.108, a considerable degree of pleasure for these parents/guardians can also be shown directly or indirectly (0.9×0.12). The distance of TASKA from home, the medium of language used, the fees charged, the curriculum supplied, and the age of their children are the primary factors that encourage their selection of TASKA (Hu et al., 2018). These caregivers have a high level of acknowledgement, which can be shown directly or indirectly (Wang et al., 2004). In addition to TASKA selection parameters, fee indications are a reason for the convenience provided by a TASKA (McNaughton, 1994). The rates also reflect the services offered (Rusbult et al., 1998). The large direct and indirect impact demonstrates the overall degree of service quality. Because these key decisions are based on three mediators: facilities, hygiene, and protection, the highest level of education among the caregivers have an indirect influence on the quantity of acknowledgement. To summarise, combining these five mediators results in a high-quality service provided (by caregivers) that approximates a complete structured equation model, with demographic factors supporting the TASKA leverage factor.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Ahmetoğlu, E., & Acar, İ. H. (2017). Parents'satisfaction With Their Children's Educational Experiences In Early Childhood Period. *Electronic Turkish Studies*, 12(6).
- Anderson, J. C., & Gerbing, D. W. (1984). The effect of sampling error on convergence, improper solutions, and goodness-of-fit indices for maximum likelihood confirmatory factor analysis. *Psychometrika*, 49(2), 155-173.

- Austin, P. C., Lee, D. S., & Leckie, G. (2020). Comparing a multivariate response Bayesian random-effects logistic regression model with a latent variable item response theory model for provider profiling on multiple binary indicators simultaneously. *Statistics in Medicine*.
- Bentler, P. M. (1990). Comparative fit indexes in structural models. *Psychological Bulletin*, 107(2), 238.
- Bentler, P. M., & Bonett, D. G. (1980). Significance tests and goodness of fit in the analysis of covariance structures. *Psychological Bulletin*, 88(3), 588.
- Berti, S., Cigala, A., & Sharmahd, N. (2019). Early Childhood Education and Care Physical Environment and Child Development: State of the art and Reflections on Future Orientations and Methodologies. *Educational Psychology Review*, 1-31.
- Berti, S., Cigala, A., & Sharmahd, N. (2019). Early Childhood Education and Care Physical Environment and Child Development: State of the art and Reflections on Future Orientations and Methodologies. *Educational Psychology Review*, 1-31.
- Bertrand, J., Butler, E., Fesseha, E., Maich, K., McCuaig, K., McLean, C., ... & Gabrielle, Y. (2019, January). Quality Early Childhood Education the Need for Special Education Services: A Symposium. In *2019 Conference of the Canadian Society for the Study of Education*.
- Briere, J., Runtz, M., Eadie, E., Bigras, N., & Godbout, N. (2017). Disengaged parenting: Structural equation modeling with child abuse, insecure attachment, and adult symptomatology. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 67, 260-270.
- Browne, M. W. (1993). Structured latent curve models. In *Multivariate analysis: Future directions 2* (pp. 171-197). North-Holland.
- Byrne B.M. (2013) Structural equation modeling with AMOS: basic concepts, applications, and programming. Routledge, New York
- Capmourteres V, Anand M (2016) Assessing ecological integrity: a multi-scale structural and functional approach using structural equation modeling. *Ecol Indic* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.07.006>
- Cava-Tadik, Y., Brown, G. L., & Mangelsdorf, S. C. (2020). Fathers' Satisfaction With Physical Affection Before and After the Birth of a New Baby: Cross-Parent Effects and Associations With Family Dynamics. *Journal of Family Issues*, 41(4), 415-436.
- Coakes, S. J., & Steed, L. G. (1999). *SPSS: Analysis without anguish: Versions 7.0, 7.5, 8.0 for Windows*. Jacaranda Wiley.
- Collier, J. E. (2020). Applied Structural Equation Modeling using AMOS: Basic to Advanced Techniques.
- Garn, A. C., & Webster, E. K. (2018). Reexamining the factor structure of the test of gross motor development—Second Edition: Application of exploratory structural equation modeling. *Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science*, 22(3), 200-212.

- Godbout, N., Daspe, M. È., Runtz, M., Cyr, G., & Briere, J. (2019). Childhood maltreatment, attachment, and borderline personality-related symptoms: Gender-specific structural equation models. *Psychological trauma: theory, research, practice, and policy*, 11(1), 90.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E. and Tatham, R. L. (2006). *Multivariate Data Analysis*. 6th Edition. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Hajizadeh, A., & Zali, M. (2016). Prior knowledge, cognitive characteristics and opportunity recognition. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*.
- Hox, J. J., & Bechger, T. M. (1995). Comparing and Combining Different Approaches to the Multitrait-multimethod matrix.
- Hoyle RH (2011) *Structural equation modeling for social and personality psychology*. Sage, London
- Hu, B. Y., Yang, Y., Wu, H., Song, Z., & Neitzel, J. (2018). Structural and process predictors of Chinese parental satisfaction toward early childhood education services. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 89, 179-187.
- Jacobucci, R., Grimm, K. J., & McArdle, J. J. (2017). A comparison of methods for uncovering sample heterogeneity: Structural equation model trees and finite mixture models. *Structural equation modeling: a multidisciplinary journal*, 24(2), 270-282.
- Jamaludin, H., & Mohamad, B. (2018). The Relationship between Service Quality and Parent Satisfaction in Early Childhood Education: A Study among Malaysian Government Servants at Putra Jaya. *Global Business and Management Research*, 10(3), 486.
- Kharuddin, A. F., Azid, N., Mustafa, Z., Ibrahim, K. F. K., & Kharuddin, D. (2020). Application of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) in Estimating the Contributing Factors to Satisfaction of TASKA Services in East Coast Malaysia. *Asian Journal of Assessment in Teaching and Learning*, 10(1), 69-77.
- Kline RB (2006) Reverse arrow dynamics. Formative measurement and feedback loops. In: Hancock GR, Mueller RO (eds) *Structural equation modeling: A second course*. Information Age Publishing, Greenwich
- Lachowicz, M. J., Preacher, K. J., & Kelley, K. (2018). A novel measure of effect size for mediation analysis. *Psychological Methods*, 23(2), 244.
- Marsh, H. W., & Hocevar, D. (1985). Application of confirmatory factor analysis to the study of self-concept: First-and higher order factor models and their invariance across groups. *Psychological Bulletin*, 97(3), 562.
- Maydeu-Olivares, A., Shi, D., & Fairchild, A. J. (2019). Estimating causal effects in linear regression models with observational data: The instrumental variables regression model. *Psychological methods*.
- McNaughton, D. (1994). Measuring parent satisfaction with early childhood intervention programs. *Topics in Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(1), 26-48.
- Mohajan, H. K. (2017). Two criteria for good measurements in research: Validity and reliability. *Annals of Spiru Haret University. Economic Series*, 17(4), 59-82.

- Ning, B., Ghosal, S., & Thomas, J. (2019). Bayesian method for causal inference in spatially-correlated multivariate time series. *Bayesian Analysis*, 14(1), 1-28.
- Papadaki, D., Bakas, D. N., Karamitsos, D., & Kirkham, D. (2019). Big data from social media and scientific literature databases reveals relationships among risk management, project management and project success. *Project Management and Project Success* (September 26, 2019).
- Parkes, A., Sweeting, H., & Wight, D. (2016). What shapes 7-year-olds' subjective well-being? Prospective analysis of early childhood and parenting using the Growing Up in Scotland study. *Social psychiatry and psychiatric epidemiology*, 51(10), 1417-1428.
- Rentzou, K. (2017). Using rating scales to evaluate quality early childhood education and care: reliability issues. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 25(5)
- Rentzou, K. (2017). Using rating scales to evaluate quality early childhood education and care: reliability issues. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 25(5), 667-681.
- Rusbult, C. E., Martz, J. M., & Agnew, C. R. (1998). The investment model scale: Measuring commitment level, satisfaction level, quality of alternatives, and investment size. *Personal relationships*, 5(4), 357-387.
- Scheiner, C. W., Baccarella, C. V., Feller, N., Voigt, K. I., & Bessant, J. (2016). Organizational and individual unlearning in identification and evaluation of technologies. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 20(02), 1650017.
- Shao Y, Bao W, Chen D, Eisenhauer N, Zhang W, Pang X, Xu G, Fu S (2015) Using structural equation modeling to test established theory and develop novel hypotheses for the structuring forces in soil food webs. *Pedobiologia* 58(4):137-145
- Shipley, B. (2016). *Cause and correlation in biology: a user's guide to path analysis, structural equations and causal inference with R*. Cambridge University Press.
- Silver, R. B., Newland, R. P., Hartz, K., Jandasek, B., Godoy, L., Lingras, K. A., ... & Seifer, R. (2017). Integrating early childhood screening in pediatrics: A longitudinal qualitative study of barriers and facilitators. *Clinical Practice in Pediatric Psychology*, 5(4), 426.
- Wang, M., Turnbull, A. P., Summers, J. A., Little, T. D., Poston, D. J., Mannan, H., & Turnbull, R. (2004). Severity of disability and income as predictors of parents' satisfaction with their family quality of life during early childhood years. *Research and Practice for Persons with Severe Disabilities*, 29(2), 82-94.
- Wheaton, B., Muthen, B., Alwin, D. F., & Summers, G. F. (1977). Assessing reliability and stability in panel models. *Sociological methodology*, 8, 84-136.
- Yilmaz, S., Daly, S. R., Seifert, C. M., & Gonzalez, R. (2016). Evidence-based design heuristics for idea generation. *Design Studies*, 46, 95-124.
- Zainudin, A. (2012). *Research Methodology and Data Analysis 5th Edition*. Shah Alam: Universiti Teknologi MARA Publication Center (UiTM Press).